

Challenge and Benefits of Online Education

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**Basundhara
Kumari**

Associate Professor
Department Of B.Ed.
Gautam Buddha Teachers'
Training College
Hazaribag, Jharkhand,
India

Abstract

COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on educational system, resulted in an unexpected shift from traditional learning to what might be referred to as e – learning. Digital platforms like ZOOM, Google Meet, Google- Classrooms etc. Online teaching and learning are faculty – delivered instruction via the Internet. Online instruction includes real – time means anywhere and anytime interaction. There are two approaches to online learning have emerged **Synchronous and Asynchronous learning**. Synchronous learning is instruction and collaboration in “**real time**” via the internet. Such as live chat audio – video conferencing, application and data sharing, using and sharing white board, virtual hand raising, data and application sharing, multimedia presentation and online slide show. **Asynchronous learning method use the time – delayed capabilities of the Internet**. This involves tools, such as: e-mail, threaded discussion, newsgroups, bulletin boards and file attachments.

Keywords Online – Learning, Digital – Platforms, Internet, Students, Learning, Teaching, Education.

Introduction

After Covid-19 the use of online education has completely changed and become necessity Covid-19 pandemic had an impact on educational system resulted in an unexpected shift from traditional (face to face) learning to what might be referred to as e-learning.

It is because of online education that in tough time education did not stop rather new opportunities and areas where opened.

Education in this century has got revolutionized and the goal is to make students skilled so that they can support themselves and make the most of their lives.

The new normal relies more on digital models which combine online and in person education have become standard. This change sought to make learning more approachable and flexible.

For B.Ed. trainees and teacher trainer's this change presented both opportunities and challenges. The effects of the pandemic on education system may differ from country to country based on infrastructure and content quality.

The study contains equalities research on the online teaching and learning experience faced by the teacher trainers and trainees.

Aim of study

Importance of online Education in present scenario

Many educational institutions and students today are moving towards online digital course in almost every field since Covid-19 the usage of language learning apps, and online learning appeared online learning software has increased dramatically.

Review of Literature

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to learning. British Journal of Educational Technology, 42(2), 233-250.

Bates, A. W. & Poole, G. (2003). Effective teaching with technology in higher education: Foundations for success. Indianapolis, IN: Jossey-Bass.

Bonk, C. J. & Graham, C. R. (Eds.). (2005). Handbook of blended learning: Global Perspectives, local designs. San Francisco, CA: Pfeiffer Publishing.

Main Text

Benefits of online Education –

Student centered-

Better opportunity-

Cost effective-

Chance for interactive-

Flexibility-

Accessibility-

Global knowledge-

Student control study-

Need of this topic:-

i. To integrate to develop a critical attitude in teachers and students about online learning.

ii. To create a community that can work together towards a common goal of using technology to help meet curricular goals.

iii. To integrate technology more effectively into teaching practice.

iv. To use these platform fully and make the experience profitable .

v. Some reforms and advancement in this filed of education is also required

vi. There is boom in online platforms and due to that the whole scenario of education has changed.

vii. There is need that both educators and learners make themselves aware of the benefits and challenge of online learning.

viii. Education in this century has got revolutionized and goal is to make students skilled so that they can support themselves and make the most of online.

Benefits of online Education

Digital learning platform give students access to high quality educational content that's accompanied by recordings, perdures and riders that are engaging as well as education.

These are benefits of online education

Reviews lectures in instantly.

Less intimidating.

More time to think before sharing.

Focus on Ideas.

Effective group communication.

Flexible learning schedule.

Cast effector.

Diversity.

Instructor Available.

Wide range of courses.

Challenge of online education:-

Sense of isolation.

Lack of focus.

Difficult to know learning abilities of students.

Reduce attention span of students.

Threat of digital eye strain.

Entire responsibilities is of students.

Teachers are not trained technically.

Fundamental problem like internet connection, proper training.

Findings

- i) So many students who find it good to boost their knowledge through online
- ii) They give more flexibility, but satisfies revved that many students are likely to struggle more with online settings
- iii) it is growing very vastly in recent years
- iv) In the age of technology and globalization, where everything is at ones fingertips
- v) Virtual existence has become the new reality
- vi) Though there are both benefit and challenges of online education, but it is the need of time hence can not be ignored

Conclusion

To overcome this problem hybrid mode can be adopted. It helps students to understand concept more quickly and in short period of time. Student can view online lectures and other resources online on their own and then come to class ready to go further with what they covered. As there is a revolutionary change in the field of education. We cannot be completely dependent on online mode and can not leave offline learning mode as well.

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